

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on choosing an assessment method

Full resource

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Introduction

Summary

The aim of the guide is to support the selection of methods, indicators and research information infrastructures (databases) for a research assessment (RA) process and to ensure that they all are aligned with what is valued and with the purpose and context of the assessment. This guide is relevant for all involved in a RA process and can be used e.g. during a recruiting process, when planning research strategy or rewarding, and in all kinds of research evaluation processes and for all disciplines.

Key aspects for reflection are discussed including the maturity of an organisation in relation to responsible RA (RRA), prioritization of values, the extent to which the diversity of research is understood and the goals an assessment process serves. The aims of research assessment are explored based on the interpretation by the [European Commission](#) (2019) according to which aims are categorized into three: monitoring, learning and improvement, and resource allocation and career development.

In this guide indicators are discussed only shortly on a general level. Most commonly used indicators are discussed in more detail in the Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>. Explore also Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research open science <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>. Open science indicators are discussed in the Open science assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to Open Science (OS). Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as check existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for the stages O and P.

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Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Reflections before starting an assessment process

Research assessment is in the middle of a cultural change where the dominance of quantitative methods is questioned. By taking small steps and making responsible choices, change is possible. Driven by academic institutions and research funding bodies, the research assessment landscape is shifting to enhance transparency and accessibility of research valuing e.g. open scholarship and preprints.

Maturity in RRA

The maturity level of an organization in relation to RRA reform affects all evaluation and assessment processes. Through internal discussion, and planning and measuring ongoing RRA practices the maturity level of RRA evolves bit by bit.

- Explore and complete the Assessment readiness template <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525577>.
- Familiarize yourself with the Guide for assembling an assessment team <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548>.

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Values

Defining and documenting values using e.g. [Value statement template](#) form the basis for selection of appropriate assessment methods, indicators etc.

Based on the SCOPE definition, a value is a judgment made about what is important and what is valued. Value judgments can be done at different granularity levels. The goals of RA reflect values like diversity of research outputs and activities, open science and transparency, multi- and interdisciplinarity, quality of research, societal impact of research, multistakeholder partnership or responsible research(er) assessment. Values must be taken into account when selecting assessment methods or deciding about use of metrics or choosing research information infrastructures (databases, data sources).

Value statement template <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524532>.

Diversity of research

Research and researchers contribute much more than just publications, and there is a wide range of roles and competencies in research. Different outputs and activities are valued at various stages of a researcher's career, and researchers are not expected to excel in all areas. In other words, emphasis is also placed e.g. on teaching and leadership tasks in addition to core research activities. Alongside this diversity, transparency in research is a key principle of responsible research and RRA.

In a narrative CV researchers use their own words and expressions to describe contributions to the generation of knowledge, contribution to the development of individuals or contribution to broader society and wider research community. Also, using multiple sources of information for assessment provides a more comprehensive picture of research outputs and activities and their openness.

Examples of the diversity of research outputs and activities:

- publications: scientific, intended for the professional community, guides, policy recommendations, patents, popular publications, conference abstracts and posters etc.
- data, programs, software etc.; audiovisual publications
- artistic and design outputs and activities
- infrastructures
- lectures and presentations
- research and innovation processes
- conferences: participation, organising
- teaching, supervising and mentoring; learning methods and tools
- science communication; acting as an expert
- activities in social media; interactions with decision-makers; citizen science
- entrepreneurship and innovations; commercialisation of research; collaboration with businesses

- contributions to meet UN's Sustainable Development Goals
- editorial work, peer reviews, steering groups
- leadership, supervisory and administrative work
- contributions to foster responsible and open science
- general skills and competencies of a researcher

The [Open and Universal Science \(OPUS\) project](#) supports reforms in research assessment to better reward OS practices. A survey of 109 experts from 22 countries - mainly from research-performing organizations, along with funders and private sector representatives - shows a strong emphasis on open access, while many other OS aspects receive less attention.

Goals of assessment

Selection of assessment methods and research information infrastructures reflects the values and goals set for the assessment.

The ultimate aims of an assessment process can be e.g. understanding, “showing off”, comparing and benchmarking, incentivising and rewarding. The [European Commission report](#) (2019) presents the following dimensions to be considered in research(er) assessment:

- Monitoring is used to gain an overall picture of research activities for a variety of purposes, often informing and justifying policies at national and international levels. E.g. benchmarking and showcasing with similar.
- Learning & improvement instead goes deeper and is closely linked to the context of the assessment having concrete goals with real actions. E.g. supporting strengths of the researcher.
- Resource allocation & career assessment concerns e.g. researcher’s tenure career path. E.g. hiring the most appropriate and potential applicants for open positions.

Assessment method

Consideration of assessment methods

When assessing research, advantages and limitations of chosen methodology should be carefully explored. The selection of the methodology starts by looking at the values and the aims of the assessment process. Is quantity valued over quality or vice versa? Is the aim of assessment “judging” or facilitation and supporting behavior? What research outputs and activities are assessed? Is the diversity of research understood and acknowledged?

Research assessment must carefully consider its broader impacts. Regardless of the methods used, evaluating research can have significant consequences which concerns especially at the individual

researchers. Consequences may include increased stress for researchers and administrators, strained collegial relationships, biased or unfair outcomes, and a disconnect between assessments and institutional values or missions. (Himanen et al., 2024)

Size and type of the entity to be assessed affects RA methodology. When assessing an individual researcher, qualitative evaluation and peer review are prior methods and quantitative indicators are used only to support expert evaluation. Use of journal-based metrics is prohibited e.g. by many funders according to the [DORA Declaration](#) when assessing individual researchers.

Quantitative methods are usable and practicable in the cases of big entities like organization, country or whole discipline. Then the purpose of assessment can be e.g. benchmarking with similar or planning research strategy. Besides quantitative methods, self-evaluation reports are an opportunity for an entity to reflect assessment against the entity's aims and strategy.

From the point of view of the whole, the validity, reliability and comprehensiveness of the assessing process should be considered. The aim is to get a balanced and multidimensional view of research or researcher using relevant resources and considering costs and benefits also. Using more than one method is often recommendable.

Assessing in collaboration with the evaluated is one SCOPE principle. Also, results of assessment should always be co-interpreted by and with the community assessed.

Figure 2 presents the impact of assessment for entities of different sizes and contexts. In the case of an individual researcher assessment has the strongest effect.

		Country	HEI	Group	Individual
Analysis	To understand	Low impact	Low impact	Medium impact	Medium impact
Advocacy	To show off	Low impact	Low impact	Medium impact	Medium impact
Accountability	To monitor	Low impact	Medium impact	Medium impact	High impact
Acclaim	To benchmark	Medium impact	High impact	High impact	High impact
Adaptation	To incentivise	Medium impact	High impact	High impact	High impact
Allocation	To reward	High impact	High impact	High impact	High impact

■ Low impact

■ Medium impact

■ High impact

Figure 2. SCOPE 'Context' Matrix defining where assessments may have a low/medium/high impact on the assessed entity (from *The SCOPE Framework: a five-stage process for evaluating responsibly*: <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>).

Glänzel, W. (2015) presents the weight of qualitative and quantitative methods against the unit to be assessed from macro to micro level.

Figure 3. Weight of qualitative and quantitative methods by Glänzel, W. (2015).

RA methods can roughly be categorized into qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative methods, done by experts, focus on the quality and trustworthiness of research whereas quantitative methods use numerical data and statistical analysis to evaluate research. Table 1 introduces main characteristics, considerations and limitations of most used assessment methods.

Table 1. Research(er) assessment methods.

Method	Main characteristics	Considerations and limitations
Qualitative, peer review, expert evaluation	<p>In line with the RRA declaration and recommendations.</p> <p>Prior method for assessment of an individual researcher e.g. in recruiting processes or to support professional development.</p> <p>A wider range of information infrastructures, data sources and documents can be used e.g. ORCID and narrative CV.</p>	<p>Careful selection of the evaluators is important. Things to consider e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject competence • Biases between evaluators and evaluands • Gender equality <p>Slow and expensive.</p> <p>Takes a lot of resources and that´s why is not very practical for assessment of big entities like countries or disciplines.</p> <p>Read more: Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025.</p>
Quantitative, metrics, use of metrics indicators	<p>Publication metrics (or bibliometrics) are the most well-known metrics. It refers to quantitative analysis of publications resulting in statistical data.</p> <p>Cost effective and quick.</p> <p>Metrics can be used for all entities in a responsible way, and it is a useful tool for understanding e.g. research trends. However, suitability for different disciplines varies as well as suitability for applied sciences.</p> <p>Useful for assessment of organizations or countries e.g. when planning research strategy.</p>	<p>When assessing an individual researcher, the principles of responsible research assessment must be taken into account. Qualitative assessment should be the prior method and quantitative metrics only support peer review.</p> <p>Responsible use takes into account e.g. the publishing practices and differences between disciplines.</p> <p>Indicators should be in line with the target or objectives of assessment.</p> <p>Can have unintended consequences if focus is on quantity over quality.</p> <p>Indicator transparency including data, definitions, algorithms, awareness of known biases, rationale of source selection should be carefully explored and reflected. One or more metrics as the quantitative input should</p>

	<p>Usually looks back and does not predict the future.</p> <p>Altmetrics tracks the mentions in social media and mass media and citations to policy papers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goes beyond the traditional bibliometrics • Indicates the social impact of research 	<p>always be used as using multiple indicators provides a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of research compared to relying on a single metric.</p> <p>The relevance of quantitative indicators decreases for smaller publication sets.</p>
<p>Narratives e.g. impact stories.</p> <p>Narrative CV</p>	<p>Impact stories are useful e.g. for monitoring open science or research funding.</p> <p>An impact narrative is a compelling statement that spells out a researcher's contributions to knowledge, health, environment, economy, society or culture. It is about going behind numbers and providing contextual information.</p> <p>Narrative CV is recommended to be used for assessment of an individual researcher. Enables a balanced and multidimensional view of a researcher. Is in line with the declarations related to responsible assessment.</p>	<p>Use of narrative CV is not yet well established.</p> <p>Subject of evaluation, researchers and evaluators need training and support.</p> <p>Time consuming for researchers and evaluators.</p> <p>Read more:</p> <p>Bernard Becker, guide on Telling Your Story - Research Impact - BeckerGuides at Becker Medical Library</p> <p>Bauman, J.R. Maximize your research impact with storytelling. Nat Rev Cancer 23, 799 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41568-023-00616-z</p>
<p>Self-assessment, self-evaluation reports</p>	<p>Useful e.g. for research assessment exercises (RAE) of organizations or assessment of research groups.</p> <p>Can be a starting point of an assessment process.</p>	<p>Can be biased and lack feedback from others.</p>
<p>Survey</p>	<p>Useful when the aim is to describe e.g. opinions and courses of</p>	<p>Can be laborious to conduct and interpret.</p> <p>Sometimes it is difficult to get replies.</p>

	action of a very large group or many groups.	Combining quantitative and qualitative surveys allow for a better output.
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Use of metrics and indicators

Metrics refers to quantitative analysis of research outputs resulting in statistical data. According to Tripathy and Vanz. (2021) metrics is a system or standard of measurement and indicator a measurement used to indicate a value of judgement.

Several declarations require a careful and responsible use of metrics and indicators in the assessment of research. Most well-known declarations are [Leiden Manifesto](#), [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#) and [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#)

The Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) has published [new principles](#) (2024) for using quantitative indicators:

1. Be clear: State the rationale for using this indicator.
2. Be transparent: State how indicators will be used.
3. Be specific: Consider how well the indicator refers to particular research or an individual researcher.
4. Be contextual: Remember that indicators are proxies, not direct measurements.
5. Be fair: Avoid biases as much as possible.

The key message of the DORA Declaration is eliminating journal-based metrics in assessment of researchers. Leiden Manifesto highlights variation of field and discipline in citation metrics. CoARA emphasizes the diversity of research, responsible use of quantitative indicators, abandoning journal-based metrics and avoiding university rankings.

There are several global research assessment reforms and Karen Stroobants asks “*Can global reform efforts be diverse and aligned?*”. Stroobants (2024) calls for reforms that are “as aligned as possible, but as diverse as necessary” and suggests more efforts to frame and align reform movements around RRA principles.

Use of metrics and indicators has challenges. There are no precise black or white rules for the use of metrics and indicators other than when they are used for the assessment and evaluation of an individual researcher. Indicators must always be in line with the target of assessment which is strongly determined by the values. It is also good to use more than one indicator as quantitative input.

Databases do not cover all possible available data and publications from all fields of science are not equally covered. Publication and citation traditions vary. Classification of fields of science in different

databases is not similar. Deficiencies in data quality are a common challenge. Indicators for e.g. open and responsible science, teaching, collaboration and other research activities are missing and waiting to be developed in most databases. First and foremost, the responsible and diverse assessment of research remains too narrow in light of mere metrics which usually looks back and does not predict the future.

Metrics are useful for research assessment of big entities like countries and big organizations with qualitative assessment and/or self-assessment on the side. In fact, metrics can be used for all entities if used responsibly. Especially when assessing an individual researcher, the principles of responsible research assessment must be considered. Weight of metrics for individuals is significantly greater than for bigger entities like organizations, and metrics for assessment of individuals should be used only to support qualitative assessment.

Use of indicators based on publications are discussed in more detail in

- Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>

Open science indicators are discussed in the

- Open science assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>

Research information infrastructures

Assessment should be done using the most relevant data sources from the point of view of the aims of assessment and not be limited to be done with the most commonly used and traditional data sources. External drivers like e.g. “old established practices” or economic factors, such as existing agreements with commercial publishers, should not be considered. Besides data sources this concerns also assessment methodology and use of metrics.

An important data source is the narrative CV with a list of research outputs and activities delivered by the researcher e.g. for a recruiting process. Look SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>.

Signatories of the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) (2024) commit to openness of all research information, meaning services and systems, infrastructures and used and produced research information.

Examples of criteria for choosing research information infrastructure (database):

- Freely accessible or subject to a charge
- Openness of all contents and files, free full texts
- Transparent indexing policy

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- Coverage: geographical, lingual, periodical
- Coverage of fields of research and disciplines
- Publication types indexed
- Research activities indexed
- Indicators available
- Visualizing tool available
- Update frequency
- Interoperability with other systems
- APIs

Table 2. Examples of open research information infrastructures compliant with Barcelona Declaration in alphabetical order.

Data source	Publisher, contents	Access
BIP!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/data • Published by IMSI, the Information Management Systems Institute in Athens • Can be customized to local knowledge bases on request • Data - mostly publications - are from OpenAIRE Graph 	Free, no charges
CRIS-systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-house systems • Pure by Elsevier Subject to a charge • Converis by Clarivate Subject to a charge • Knowledge base of CRIS-system varies from organization to other 	Commercial systems subject to a charge. Often open.
Dimensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.dimensions.ai/ • Published by Digital Science • Collection of linked research outputs including e.g. publications, datasets, patents, policy documents. • Read more 	Free version for personal and non-commercial use Dimension Analytics version subject to a charge

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<p>Google Scholar</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://scholar.google.com/ • No exact information about content, coverage or update frequency • Covers equally all disciplines and fields of science • Consist both scientific and non-scientific research outputs and citations • Limited sorting and analyzing tools • Well known and widely used by researchers 	<p>Free, no charges</p>
<p>ORCID</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORCID • The international ORCID identifier (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) provides a permanent and unique digital identifier for a researcher. ORCID ID a series of numbers that will distinguish you from other researchers. • Registration needed. • Updates and visibility depend on researcher ´s activity. • Biograph, employment, education and qualifications, professional activities, funding and works can be added. • Can be used to complement a researcher ´s CV. 	<p>Free, no charges</p>
<p>OpenAlex</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User interface https://openalex.org/ • Published by OurResearch.org • A wide list of data sources, research outputs and entities which are tagged with topics using an automated system that takes into account available information about the work, including title, abstract, source (journal) name and citations. There are around 4500 topics • Data is extracted from a variety of sources like ORCID, ROR, DOAJ, Unpaywall, Pubmed, arXiv, Zenodo 	<p>Website, API and data snapshot free.</p> <p>Premium and institutional versions subject to a charge</p>

OpenCitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://opencitations.net/ • Run by David Shotton, University of Oxford and Silvio Peroni, University of Bologna • Database maintained by OpenCitations is COCI, the OpenCitations Index of Crossref Open DOI-to-DOI Citations 	Free, no charges
OpenAIRE and OpenAIRE Graph	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://graph.openaire.eu/ • Published by the European Union • Sources: e.g. Open Access journals registered in DOAJ, Crossref, Unpaywall, ORCID, Microsoft Academic Graph, Datacite. Repositories registered in OpenDOAR, re3data.org, FAIRSharing.org and many others • OpenAIRE Graph enables powerful ways of using data programmatically for free • OpenAIRE Explore is user friendly way for exploring the OpenAIRE Graph 	Free, no charges
OPERAS Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OPERAS Metrics (open scholarly communications in the european research area for social sciences and humanities) • OPERAS Metrics provides usage and impact information for published Open Access books 	Free to access the database, no charges.
PlumX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PlumX Metrics Uncover and tell the stories of research Elsevier • Published by Elsevier • Citations, usage, captures, mentions, social media • Goes beyond the traditional bibliometrics 	<p>Widget can be freely integrated to non-commercial OA-journals and regional repositories, upon request and approval</p> <p>For data providers and platform partners widget is</p>

		subject to a charge
Publish or Perish, PoP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish • Managed by professor Harzing • Tool for analyzing Google Scholar materials but also citations from other sources like Crossref, PubMed, Scopus or Web of Science 	Free, no charges
Unpaywall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unpaywall: An open database of 20 million free scholarly articles • Harvests OA content from over 50 000 publisher and repositories • For libraries, enterprises and researchers • Widely integrable to a variety of databases and systems 	Free, no charges

Table 3. Examples of commercial research information infrastructures in alphabetical order.

Data source	Publisher, contents	Access
Altmetric.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.altmetric.com/ • Published by Digital Science • Online and mass media attention beyond bibliometrics (societal impact of research) 	Subject to a charge
DataCite Commons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://commons.datacite.org/ • Connects research outputs and resources • Governed by its members 	Charges depend on use of DataCite services
Overton	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overton • Citations to policy papers answering to the question has research influenced decision making • Goes beyond the traditional publication metrics 	Subject to a charge

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follows governmental document, think tanks etc from all over the world 	
Scopus / SciVal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus preview - Scopus - Welcome to Scopus • Published by Elsevier • Includes millions of research publications including articles, books, conference papers, patents etc. • Indexing policy is open • Dominance of English language • SciVal is a research benchmarking and visualizing tool that uses Scopus data 	Subject to a charge
Web of Science, WoS / InCites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CI Clarivate • Published by Clarivate • Platform providing access to millions of research references and citation data • Indexing policy is open • Dominance of English language • InCites is a research benchmarking and visualizing tool that uses WoS data 	Subject to a charge

Data sources cover research entities focusing mainly on publications. In table 4. research entities covered by OpenAlex, OpenAIRE and BIP!Services are listed. As can be seen many research outputs and activities are not indexed in the three databases leaving contributions other than publications out. This is a matter to be considered when making decisions about assessment protocol.

Table 4. Support for representation of research entities and output types in global platforms and models (modified from the tables in [Hyrkkänen et al. 2023](#), p. 107, 110, 113, 116).

Entity type	OpenAlex	OpenAIRE	BIP!Services
Publications	Yes	Yes	Yes
Journal articles	Yes	Yes	Yes

Scientific publications beyond journal articles	Yes	Yes	Yes
Open access publications	Yes	Yes	Yes
Funding information	Yes	Yes	Yes
Persons	Yes	Yes	Yes
Research data	Yes	Yes	Yes
Datasets	Yes	Yes	Yes
Open research data	Yes	Yes	Yes
Organization	Yes	Yes	Yes
Software	No	Yes	Yes
Training, mentoring and supervision of PhD candidates	No	Yes	Yes
CVs	No	No	Yes
Peer review	No	No	Yes
Data models	Yes	Yes	No
Policy contributions	No	Yes	No
Projects	No	Yes	No
Activities	No	Yes	No
Open source software	No	Yes	No
Infrastructures	No	Yes	No
Leadership roles	Partially	Yes	No
Theories	No	No	No
Strategies	No	No	No
Exhibitions	No	No	No
Industry-academia cooperation	No	No	No
Methods	No	No	No

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Protocols	No	No	No
Workflows	No	No	No
Algorithms	No	No	No
Skills and competencies	No	No	No
Teaching	No	Partially	No
Entrepreneurship	No	No	No
Science communication and interaction with society	No	No	No
Team science and collaboration	No	No	No
Skills, competencies and merits	No	No	No
Knowledge valorization	No	No	No
Roles outside of academia	No	No	No
Diverse contributor roles (Data steward, software engineer, and data scientists)	No	No	Partially
Citizen science	No	No	No
Other open science elements (open-science related events, courses, projects)	No	No	No

Read more: [OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report](#) by Hyrkkänen et al. (2023) presents data sources thoroughly starting from page 97.

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